

STUDIES ON GUM JEOL (*LANNEA GRANDIS*, ENGLER). PART VII. PROPERTIES OF JEOLIC ACID IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

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Hydrogen-ion activity equivalent, conductance and cataphoretic velocity vary with the concentration of the jeolic acid solution in a manner similar to that of the arabic acid.

In previous communications of this series (Parts I-VI, this *Journal*, 1948, 25) different behaviours and properties of the whole gum, purified by precipitation with alcohol, were studied with a view to determining primarily whether there was any aggregate formation in the aqueous solution of this gum, whether there was base-exchange and, if so, how far the latter could influence its viscous and electrochemical properties.

In the present paper the same study has been extended to the complex acid of gum jeol (previously referred to as the Jeolic acid in Part II) to ascertain how far the electrochemical properties of its aqueous solution are dependent on the concentration. Investigations have been carried out in the same line as indicated in the case of arabic acid (Mukherjee and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 81) with reference to the variations of hydrogen-ion activity, equivalent conductance and cataphoretic velocity with concentration.

EXPERIMENTAL

The jeolic acid solutions used in course of these investigations have been obtained by electro dialysis of the purified gum in absence of acids. It has been reported in Part IV of this series (this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 333) that this jeolic acid can be obtained by mild hydrolysis of the gum by dilute H_2SO_4 , or by electro dialysis of the gum in presence and also in absence of acids. The method of preparation based upon electro dialysis of the gum in absence of acids was preferred as in this process complications arising out of the introduction of an acid from outside were completely avoided. The acid was then precipitated by the addition of alcohol from a portion of the solution obtained by electro dialysis, washed with alcohol-ether mixture, dried and analysed by combustion yielding C, 39.1%, H, 7.6% and O, 53.2%.

A stock solution of the acid of concentration 10 g. per litre was prepared from which other concentrations were obtained by dilution. Electrochemical properties studied here comprise the measurement of p_H , specific conductance and cataphoretic speeds (c.v.) at a temperature of $35^\circ \pm 0.1$. Measurements of specific conductance were carried out at a frequency of 450 cycles approximately in a thermoionic valve oscillator. Cataphoretic measurements were carried out by the microscopic method in a flat glass cell of Freundlich and Abramson type. Ordinarily the particles could not be viewed quite clearly under the microscope (magnification about 600 times), but when the particles were in motion under an electric field, their motion could be followed. Potential gradient was measured by the help of Ohm's law from a knowledge of the specific conductance of the solution under examination.

H-ion activity or free acidity (a_H) was calculated from the p_H values in the usual manner with hydrogen electrode. Equivalent conductance cannot, however, be determined from specific conductance as the equivalent weight of the acid is not definitely known. Hence a quantity Λ has been calculated which refers to the conductance offered by that volume of the solution as contains 1 g. of the acid. This quantity will be strictly proportional to the equivalent conductance. Total titratable acidity (C_H) was determined by potentiometric titration of the acid with NaOH. Since C_H measures the concentration of the jeolic acid in equivalents (as obtained by titration with NaOH), the ratio a_H/C_H measures the hydrogen-ion activity per equivalent of the acid at any concentration and is a measure of the degree of dissociation or the activity coefficient (f) at that concentration.

DISCUSSION

Hydrogen-ion Activity.—Table I shows the variation of H-ion activity.

TABLE I
Jeolic acid solution.
Temp. = $35^{\circ} \pm 0.1$.

Conc. (g./litre)	p_{H}	Free acidity or H-ion activity.	Total acidity ($C_{\text{H}} \times 10^4 N$)	$a_{\text{H}}/C_{\text{H}}$ ratio (=f).	C.V. in cm./sec/volt/cm. $\times 10^4$.
0.7	3.93	1.17	6.31	0.185	1.79
1.0	3.06	3.21	9.01	0.245	2.34
3.0	3.26	5.31	27.10	0.197	2.07
4.0	3.20	6.36	35.85	0.171	1.74
5.0	3.17	6.81	45.16	0.157	1.50
7.0	3.07	8.57	64.0	0.134	1.24
10.0	2.88	15.32	89.6	0.174	1.28

The plot of a_{H} against concentration (c) shown in Fig. 1 (curve 1) exhibits a small buffer region extending approximately from a concentration of 4 g. to 6 g. of the acid per litre. This presents a point of contrast of this acid with arabic acid where the a_{H} increases with concentration uneventfully along a smooth curve (Mukherjee and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*, p. 84, Fig. 2). Whether this peculiarity is in any way associated with the behaviour of the whole gum itself, which shows little variation of H-ion activity with concentration of its aqueous solution (Mukherjee and Rohatgi, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 342, Table III, columns 2 and 3), is difficult to ascertain, but they appear to be mutually suggestive.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The total acidity C_{H} , however, varies linearly with concentration but the ratio $a_{\text{H}}/C_{\text{H}}$ shows a maximum and a minimum occurring at concentrations of 2.0 and 7 g. per litre of the acid respectively (vide Fig. 1, curve 2). In this respect the jeolic acid resembles the behaviour of the arabic acid which also shows a maximum and a minimum in the value of the ratio, at concentrations of about 1 g. and 24 g. respectively (Mukherjee and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*, Mukherjee and Bhowmik, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 152, Table I, column 5). Another interesting feature in this connection is that the value of this ratio, which serves as an approximate measure of the degree of dissociation of the acid, is quite small, the maximum value observed being near about 25% at 1% concentration of the acid. This apparently signifies that the acid is a weak one having quite a low degree of dissociation, although the potentiometric titration curve reveals the character of a strong acid which will be discussed in the next communication.

Equivalent Conductance.—In the following table the data for specific conductance and equivalent conductance (Λ) have been shown (Table II).

TABLE II
Jeolic acid solution.

Temp. = 35° ± 0.1.		Sp. cond. of water used = 1.2 × 10 ⁻⁶ mho at 35°.		
Conc. (g./litre)	C.	Specific conductance × 10 ⁵ . (obs.)	* (calc. from α_H).	Equiv. cond. in g./litre.
0.1	0.32	0.26 mho	—	2.56 mho
0.3	0.56	0.75	—	2.49
0.5	0.70	1.23	—	2.46
0.7	0.83	1.71	2.62 mho	2.45
1.0	1.00	2.38	3.60	2.36
3.0	1.73	5.53	10.80	1.34
4.0	2.00	6.74	14.34	1.60
5.0	2.24	8.00	18.06	1.60
7.0	2.65	10.44	25.60	1.49
10.0	3.16	13.57	35.84	1.36

α_H values have been taken from Table I.

Plotting Λ against \sqrt{C} a straight line graph is expected from Onsager's equation which connects Λ with \sqrt{C} by the equation, $\Lambda_0 = \Lambda_0 - k\sqrt{C}$, where Λ_0 is the value of Λ at infinite dilution and k , a constant giving the slope of the line. The actual graph is shown in Fig. 2. from which the following interesting observations are noted.

(a) Λ decreases almost linearly with \sqrt{C} up to a concentration of 1 g./litre (approx.). Beyond this point the diminution is more rapid. There is thus a kink in the curve which has been regarded by Hartley as a feature characterising the starting point of aggregates formation in solutions of colloidal electrolytes. If the kink be regarded as indicative of the starting point of aggregate formation, the concentration corresponding to the kink does not tally with the maximum of the ($\alpha_H/C_H - C$) curve.

(b) Λ does not appear to pass through a minimum.

(c) The curve extrapolated to zero concentration gives low values for the equivalent conductance calculated on the basis of the equivalent weight obtained by titration with NaOH, even lower than that of hydrogen ions alone at infinite dilution.

Moreover, as will be evident from columns 3 and 4 of Table II, the specific conductances calculated from the hydrogen-ion activity at the corresponding concentrations are always greater than the observed values. Of course, in these cases calculations have been carried out on the assumption that the equivalent conductance of H-ions at 35° is 400 mho (cf. Glasstone, "Electrochemistry of Solutions", 1937, p.72; Int. Crit. Tables, 1929, VI, 259), and that it is not influenced by presence of other ions in the solution (cf. independent migration of ions). How far such calculations are justified in these cases awaits clarification. This discrepancy between calculated and observed values of specific conductance at different concentrations are in agreement with those observed in the case of arabic acid (cf. Mukherjee and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 84, Table II, columns 3 and 5) but is just the reverse of what has been noted in the case of yeast nucleic acid (cf. Mukherjee and Sarkar, this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 72, Table V, columns 3 and 4).

Cataphoretic Mobility.—Variations of cataphoretic speeds with concentration have been shown in the last column of Table I and graphically represented in Fig. 1 (curve 3).

The graph passes through a maximum at a concentration of 1.6 g./litre and reaches a constant value at higher concentrations. Thus, the concentration, where the maximum occurs in this case, is close to that where the kink is observed to appear in $\Lambda - \sqrt{C}$ curve viz., at 1 g./litre. The curve appears to be similar in nature to that of arabic acid (cf. Mukherjee and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*).

The authors' thanks are due to Dr. H. L. Roy for his keen interest.